

**SUBSERVIENCE AND SERVILISM: MAINTENANCE OF
SUBALTERNITY AND ANTI-RACIST PERSPECTIVES IN SOLITÁRIA,
BY ELIANA ALVES CRUZ**

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Alexandra Alves da Silva

Master's student in Comparative Literature (UERJ - FFP). She has been working in basic education since 2001, as a teacher of Portuguese, Literature and Writing in primary and secondary education (private network). She is a member of the research group GEFIS (Group of Feminist and Intersectional Studies) of CNPq (PPLIN/ UERJ-FFP). Her research is centered on systemic and decolonial violence by women. Lattes: <https://lattes.cnpq.br/7045452830200358>. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1287-0559>.

Email: prof.alexandra.ead@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

The present work aims, from the reading of the recently released novel *Solitário*, by Eliana Alves Cruz, to promote some educational and anti-racist reflections inserted in the work, representing the many black voices silenced by the work as a maid. Bringing a literary comparison in this thematic clipping, the literature of Conceição Evaristo (2020) will also be worked on throughout the text. In addition to the novel's content being aligned with decolonial and intersectional thinking, the author's incursion into the verisimilar work is also significant, as she appropriates a literature whose speech space denounces the permanence of colonial practices as a strong political project. Under the theoretical support of authors such as Beatriz Nascimento (2021), Françoise Vergès (2022), Lélia Gonzalez (2020) and Sueli Carneiro (2011), I emphasize the idea that the aforementioned novel challenges the maintenance of work slaves in Brazil, as well as investigating our own ancestry, the erased and/or silenced history and the memory of enslaved Africans, rescuing what was lost in the process of imposing colonialist power. Starting from events that recall recent Brazilian issues, the stories of the women of *Solitaire* intertwine with ours, denouncing the crimes committed against people of African descent: from slavery to the present day.

Keywords: Intersectionality. Decolonialism. Female authority. Afro-Brazilian Literature. Feminist literary criticism.

*The cheapest meat on the market
It's black meat (You know it's not easy, right, bro?) Check it out
The cheapest meat on the market is black meat (4x)
(Only-only blind can't see)*

That goes to prison for free
And goes under plastic And goes to underemployment And to psychiatric hospitals for free
The cheapest meat on the market is black meat (They say it around)
The cheapest meat on the market is black meat (3x)
Who made and makes history
Holding this country in his arm, my brother The goat who doesn't feel revolted Because the revolver is
already cocked And the chosen avenger But very well intentioned
And this country is making everyone black
And their hair straight But even so, it still keeps the right
From some ancestor of color
Subtly fight for respect Fight bravely for respect Fight for justice and respect (believe me)
From some ancestor of the color
Fight, fight, fight, fight, fight Check it out.
 (...)

Composers: Marcelo Fontes Do Nascimento Santana / Seu Jorge / Ulises Capelleti

In 2002, the song *A carne*, interpreted by the powerful voice of Elza Soares, opens up denunciations regarding some issues faced by black people in Brazil: underemployment, overcrowding in prisons, the enslavement of ancestors, guns pointed at racialized people, it seems that it is necessary to fight, fight all the time to defend against structural racism and open wounds, consequences of 300 years of slavery in Brazil. There are many years of silencing, of a history told in books by the hegemonic vision of the colonizers, that is, when will we be able to effectively think about democracy if even Brazilians do not know their own history, or worse: they ignore the indigenous and black blood spilled until today so that if what we consider our homeland were built?

In this sense, it is necessary to decolonize the way in which the thinking of the maintainers of this class, race and even gender structure was implemented, since everyone needs to have a voice; it is necessary to deconstruct the narratives with a single point of view. Thus, aiming at such a change, we educators encourage the need to implement a literature, an anti-racist and engaged training so that there is equity between people. With this, I bring the literature of Eliana Alves Cruz with her didactic and sensitive writing to address themes such as silencing and maintenance of ills that still affect black men and women in Brazil. To carry out these conclusions, the novel *Solitário* (2022), a work that displaces readers from their perspectives, will guide reflections on some structures of racism in our country, however, as there are many pertinent themes in the book, I will stick to the excerpt of issues related to the maintenance of black women's workforce in subordinate functions.

Eliana Alves Cruz stands out as one of the most important voices of contemporary female authorship, because she adds to her malleability with words the providential decolonial

factors that Brazil needs: historical review of perpetuated racist behaviors, lack of recognition of one's own race, denial of ancestry, religious intolerance – when the manifestations belong to African matrices –, silencing in the face of the most diverse situations, lack of composition in political positions... there are so many open wounds in this country that is formed by us (as a personal pronoun of the straight case or substantive). All of Eliana's work, with her sensitivity in constructing the subjectivities of each character, brings anti-racist themes and, in addition, manages to address these points in a simple way, representing the power of yet another very talented voice, such as that of Elsa Soares, contributing to the deconstruction of prejudices and unacceptable behavior.

On the margins, the speeches: literature as spaces of representation

To think of female bodies as social elements of resistance through the vulnerabilities to which they are subjected is to reflect on the simplicity of how the author explored the narrative focuses of the book. The novel has three narrators in the first person, which gives a lot of reliability in relation to the facts experienced. In the first part, the voice is that of Mabel, Eunice's daughter, a young reader of Conceição Evaristo who begins to question the racist and classist attitudes of her mother's employers, as well as to bring about striking reflections in relation to gender, class and race: “ Mom, you need to get rid of these people. You don't owe them anything. Don't be afraid to face these people who have never cleaned their own toilet!” (CRUZ, 2022, p.11). Despite all the adversities that could determine her lack of prospects for the future, through education, she manages to break paradigms, transform her own reality and that of the people around her. She became a doctor and a source of inspiration for other black girls whose dreams seem to be hampered by the painful reality and, perhaps because of this, the novel bumps into the wound of the demonization of racial quotas, since the elite does not want to find the children of maids in the hallways of public universities, occupying leadership positions, or even having any services provided by blacks that are outside the scope of subservience and subalternity:

Dr Mabel was very worried. (...) When he was starting to prepare Bruninho for intubation, he heard a voice somewhere in the ICU that seemed familiar to him. How could they be fighting in a place like this? (...) A few beds away, a patient refused to receive medication from the hands of a black nurse. (CRUZ, 2022, p.154)

In the second part, the voice belongs to Eunice, a woman who perpetuated the maintenance of the work of racialized women in the homes of wealthy families and dedicated her entire life – including her childhood – to domestic work: “children like me – how she was and, before her, her mother, and her mother's mother, even my grandmother – they didn't quite understand what it was like to be a child” (p.26). Nor was she aware that the bosses enslaved her with exhausting and inhuman working hours, without rest, without a signed work permit and without adequate pay for the tasks duly performed; days off were only one Sunday a fortnight. When the wealthy couple (Seu Thiago and D. Lúcia) announced that they would have a baby (Camilinha), Eunice, who had just been fired – probably intentionally so that her salary would be cut even further –, was rehired by her boss, but with an observation: “we will have a lot of new and unpredictable expenses, said Seu Thiago. We're going to need to make a small adjustment to your salary” (p.30). Obviously, her salary would not make the slightest difference in the budget of those wealthy people, but the devaluation of services rendered and considered subaltern seems to be a necessity for these mediocre people, since, probably, in just one night dining out they would pay the salary of a month of Eunice. It is a representation of the maintenance of the colonial system and to prove that this behavior is perpetuated, Sueli Carneiro points out:

“In the labor market, the concrete result of this exclusion is expressed in the profile of the Black female workforce. According to data released by the Ministry of Labor and the Ministry of Justice in the publication *Brasil, Gender and Race*, "black women engaged in manual activities make up a total of 79.4%". Of these, 51% are allocated in domestic employment and 28, 4% are washerwomen, ironers, cooks, servants. (...) When employed, black women earn on average half of what white women earn and four times less than white men. (...) The National Income between blacks and whites in minimum wages is distributed as follows: white man earns 6.3 minimum wages; white woman, 3.6; black man, 2.9; black woman, 1.7.” (CARNEIRO, 2011, p.128-9)

In the third part, the narration is in charge of the following question: what if the walls could talk? They are the “Solitaires” and it is in this that the key point of the author's didactic, striking and sensitive literature comes to the fore to move readers. The word solitary can refer us to the idea of prison, loneliness and even the way it is narrated, how it feels after being abandoned. One of several striking moments in this part of the novel is when one reflects on the impossibility of the right to childhood and, in the memories of the “Solitaires”, the names of the children of the maids, who did not experience childish age, appeared: “Ouvir a voz of Eunice made my memories run through all the non-children who passed through here. João, Pedro, Cocoa, Mabel, Irene, Gilberto, Dadá. (...) It's curious to notice how some people in this

world don't have the right to childhood. (p.144). The change in perspective of the narration makes readers realize that literature can offer countless possibilities, including thinking about how these spaces have history.

Places, walls and personified objects: the cartography of segregations

Symbolically, the spaces are integral parts of the novel, as each narrator develops the plot based on the cartography of the building, so this demarcation clearly signals the segregation between the represented classes. Mabel transports us from the simple and nostalgic backyard of her home to the Golden Plate building and introduces us to each place on the penthouse where her mother works as a luxurious setting, far from most Brazilians and with an air of imprisonment. The chapters are arranged in order to organize the scenarios and functionality of the roof: floor plan, swimming pool, kitchen, office, concierge, ballroom, baby's room, reception, bathroom, window. In these spaces, readers visit structures maintained from slavery to the present day.

In addition, conflicts between generations appear repeatedly and, in this passage, we perceive young Mabel's pain when revealing that her mother, in a perpetuation of the work of black women since the period of slavery, took care of her bosses' daughter, Camilinha, but forgot to look at her own daughter:

“I am no longer a child, mother! I grew up, I'm here in front of you. Do you know why you think I'm still a baby? Because all you see is that annoying girl! You didn't see when I got my period for the first time; saw nothing of my school; he didn't see anything about my life and he didn't see that I...” (CRUZ, 2022, p.91)

In this maintenance of spaces destined for domestic workers, we realize that the slave quarters were left with eviction rooms, or maids' rooms, whose silence and silencing function as latent remnants of slavery, since such small rooms must be close to the kitchen and the service area, they are poorly lit, hot, with little circulation and sometimes without windows. How is it possible to feel comfortable in such an environment? Another interesting survey was carried out when Eunice said: “it was like it was said in one of the books by a writer called Conceição Evaristo, which Mabel started to devour and from time to time read to me: 'in a closed mouth, no mosquitoes enter, but there are no smiles' ” (p.97) and, in Figure 01, we can see that the scarce smiles reveal an apparent suffering.

Figure 01: From the slave quarters to the eviction rooms: the suppressed smiles – enslaved women with white children of mill owners and farmers.

Source: <https://iconografiadahistoria.com.br/2020/10/25/uma-analise-sobre-a-baba-negra-na-historia-do-brasil/>. Accessed on 04/26/2023.

Just like Eunice, who once stopped mothering and giving due attention to Mabel's education to take care of Camilinha, each of these women in figure 01 gave up their own lives to take care of their children. From this perspective, the narrator talks naturally about her own silences, because she has already been used to recognizing where she can stay so as not to disturb the owners of the roof, how she should be so as not to disturb them – preferably in silence: “in addition to the tight spaces we occupied, silence was a companion. It was necessary to be present without being there. A good servant is silent, and the child that is the daughter of this woman must be too” (p. 97), or where she needs to be to meet the demands of the bosses.

Some of the spaces narrated by Eunice are: living room, garden, wall, service area, nightstand. On p.89, the title of the chapter refers to the novel by Carolina Maria de Jesus, *Quarto de despejo* and, in this chapter, we perceive yet another generational conflict and the perpetuation of stories: “I knew that she was unable to have a child, because she herself was one. But... it was my grandson or granddaughter.” (p.92). They are pains ²¹that intersect and repeat themselves between generations. In the Crystal Mirror chapter, Luzia, d. Lúcia asked Camila to stay with Gilberto, her four-year-old son, while she needed to buy the ingredients to prepare a feijoada. Due to Camila's negligence, the boy fell from the building and died instantly. (pp.: 127 to 131). It seems that the writer, also a journalist, captured the reality of recent events

²¹The pain that only black women are capable of feeling.

in the country and brought verisimilitude to the novel; it also seems that the objects and spaces on the roof are more valuable than the lives of the people who work to maintain cleanliness.

As for the last part, the “Solitárias” describe the personifications of the maid's room, the porter's room, the hospital room and the rest room, that is, these environments have histories petrified by racism and classism.

Subalternity and servility: maintenance of violence against black women

Hypothetically, one of the proposals conquered by feminism was from 1960, when white women were allowed to go out to work with the authorization of their husbands. However, who would be responsible for cleaning the house, preparing meals, taking care of the children, keeping the residences organized? Thinking about it, the elite would be able to benefit from all sides: white men worked, black men – since slavery –, white women – with a lower salary – and black women, whose salaries were even more flat, these, they always worked. Thus, black women carried all the enrichment of whites on their backs. Another possibility that is attributed to the devaluation of services such as housework is the fact that it represents work intended for women, for manual practices. According to Lélia Gonzales:

The highest concentration of the female workforce occurs in the services, social and merchandise trade sectors (domestic workers, teachers, nurses, clerks), which have expanded as a result of industrialization and modernization. But the majority of black women (69%) work in agriculture and service delivery. This means that social activities and commerce mainly absorb white women (30% to 16% black). (...) In the service sector, we find the “natural place” of black women who work in cities: domestic employment. (...) Another important aspect is the registration in the portfolio: only 40% of black workers have this labor guarantee, compared to 60% of white workers. (GONZALES, 2020, pp.192 to 194).

In this vein, bringing another literary reference and with the same focus on domestic work discussed here, we think of Maria, whose name carries the homonymous title that makes up the collection of short stories present in the book *Olhos d'água*, by Conceição Evaristo. In the story, the absences of Maria, who is also a maid, range from food to love, since she is completely unprotected and only receives leftovers and crumbs, including affection. Some subtleties can also be noticed between the characters' identification spaces: the community (Maria's space) and the asphalt (the boss's space); the bus (which looks more like the new slave ship, taking passengers to the places where they “should” be); that means of transport carries

“the cheapest meat on the market”. For having worked on Sunday, that is, for not being able to enjoy her only day off, since there was a party at her employer's house, she received payment:

She took home the remains. The ham bone and the fruit that had decorated the table. He'd earned the fruits and a tip. The bone, the mistress was going to throw it away. I was happy, despite the tiredness. The tip had come at a good time. The two youngest children had the flu. I needed to buy syrup and that medicine to unclog my nose. I could also buy a can of Toddy. The fruits were great and there was melon. The children had never eaten melon. (EVARISTO, 2020, p.39)

On the bus, he talked to the father of his eldest son, but that man ended up carrying out a robbery with a gun on public transport. She did not have her belongings taken and this attitude was crucial for her to receive a cruel sentence from the victims of the assailant. For this reason, that black female body, already so sacrificed by menial and humiliating work in the homes of wealthy bosses, was martyred when she heard “black bastard” and, when she looked in the direction of the screams from which the voice was coming, she saw a thin black boy, with boyish features reminiscent of his son. (...) That whore, that naughty black woman was with the thieves! (p.42). The social judgment was so incisive that readers are faced with the following scene:

Lynch! Lynch! Lynch! Maria was bleeding from her mouth, nose and ears. The bag had burst and the fruit was rolling across the floor. Would the boys like the melon?

Everything was so fast, so brief, Maria missed her ex-man. Why were they doing this to her? The man had whispered a hug, a kiss, a caress for his son. She needed to get home to deliver the message. They were all armed with laser knives that cut to life. When the bus emptied, when the police arrived, the woman's body was all torn apart, all trampled on. (EVARISTO, 2020, p.42)

The short story ends with this heartbreaking scene and, therefore, it is possible to raise countless hypotheses. Why did the assailant's victims attack that vulnerable black female body, even though there were requests from the driver and some passengers not to commit such an atrocity? Why is a similar person the first to attack Maria in a barbaric attitude, since everyone there was a worker, that is, they were in the same situation as her? Does the fact that those people attacked her not make them as criminal or worse than the assailant? Is all that hatred of collectively murdering Maria's black female body a hatred of the system, of life itself? What kind of justice did those people know to think they had the right to morally judge women? There are many questions, many reflections. That lady, a maid, whose three children did not have enough maternal and material assistance, did not get to know freedom or experience smiles.

All this violence, absences, including freedom of choice for black women, makes one think that, even with abolition, they were not offered the opportunity to decide whether they wanted to stay at home to take care of their children, or work outside the home, because they have always been enslaved, they needed and need resources that were and are denied to them; at no time was there any thought of freeing them from work. Thus, according to the thinker Vergès:

Violence against enslaved women is neither an unfortunate episode in an unhappy history nor the only example of colonial violence. Neglecting them perpetuates the illusion that the history of racializations during slavery would be disconnected from these gender violences – especially if we consider that abolitionism did not try to end them. (VERGÈS, 2021, p.69)

In addition to the issue of the freedom that black women theoretically have today, the perpetuation of this very marked caste system in Brazil is perpetuated, because in the past they were the cooks in the main house and the slave quarters, they were kept pregnant - many through rape – to offer milk to the children of the mistresses, in addition to, with these pregnancies, offering new slaves to the owners of the farms, thus increasing their wealth. Afterwards, consequently, and although “free”, they were kept in the houses being exploited until their death, as they were considered “part of the family”, but without being included in terms of the division of property. These colonial practices remain and the researcher Beatriz Nascimento, in her work *A story made by black hands*, points out:

Unlike the white woman, her counterpart at the other pole, the black woman, can be considered an essentially productive woman, with a role similar to that of her man, that is, endowed with an active role. First of all, as a slave, she is a worker, not only in the tasks of the big house (an activity that is not limited to satisfying the pampering of the masters, ladies and their children, but also as a producer of food for the slaves) as well as also in the field, in the subsidiary activities of cutting and milling. On the other hand, in addition to her productive capacity, due to her condition as a woman and, therefore, as a potential mother of new slaves, she had the function of reproducing new merchandise for the internal labor market. (BIRTH, 2021, p.56)

Since *Lolita* is a book that touches on Brazilian wounds, the dedication itself is already strong, because Eliana writes: “For my aunt Maria da Glória, Dodó, whose face I never saw and whose only thing I know is that work never freed her” and we are surprised when in the pages of the novel, Dadá, a lady of around 40 years old with the behavior of a child, dialogues with one of the boys who lives in the Golden Plate and reveals that there are citizens who literally still keep people enslaved, with that we have the notion of his tragedy:

- God forbid, young man” Mãezinha Imaculada is capable of hitting me with her slipper...
- (...)
- Dada, how old are you?
- “Forty...I think.
- Since when have you been with Imaculada?
- Since I was ten.” (CRUZ, 2022, pp.: 120 to 122)

Just like Eliana's aunt Dodó, Dadá was another person without the right to childhood, without being able to choose her own destiny, without the right to freedom. How many Dadás lived in Brazil? ²²How many are still in a situation analogous to slavery? ²³Who are interested in maintaining this inhumane practice? ²⁴Answers to questions like these seem like part of a movie: the horror genre.

Final considerations

There are countless themes that can be analyzed in *Solitário* . In this section, I tried to show how the author makes use of fiction that emphasizes domestic work to build a narrative of recovery of the enslaved experience and its forms of resistance in an interweaving of silences and silencings. In this social mosaic of maintenance of the big houses and slave quarters, we are led to reflections, to indignation in the face of a crime, whose perpetrators try to erase the evidence to leave without punishment. However, readers also experience hope, since, through education, we understand that it is possible to transform realities.

Our society was shaped by the slavery model and the structural differences generated by this social construction last until today. It is important to have access to knowledge and class recognition so that there is no burden of “gratitude” for everything the elite has done, because in fact, the objective of the wealthy classes has always been to hide information, to restrict education to those who can afford it. For her, to further flatten the wages of the working class, particularly those of black women. If we started with the democratization of basic health and education services, also offering equity in terms of access to universities and training more aware people from early childhood, then we could achieve important achievements. All people can and should fight for an anti-racist education, as this fight is for historical correction.

²² https://www.em.com.br/app/noticia/gerais/2020/12/20/interna_gerais.1222578/libertada-mineira-que-viveu-38-anos-em-regime-de-escravidao-no-state.shtml . Accessed on 11/14/2022.

²³ <https://g1.globo.com/rj/rio-de-janeiro/noticia/2022/05/13/idosa-e-resgatada-no-rio-apos-72-anos-em-situacao-analoga-a-slavery.ghtml> . Accessed on 11/14/2022.

²⁴ <https://noticias.uol.com.br/cotidiano/ultimas-noticias/2021/02/14/mpt-professora-ufrj-trabalho-escravo-idosa.htm> . Accessed on 11/14/2022.

Therefore, one should not disregard or forget that the remnants of slavery are in prejudice, in religious intolerance, in the service elevator, in the job vacancy for “good-looking people”, that is, each of these episodes of racism hurts like a cut. razor on the “cheapest meat on the market”. In this sense, Eliana Alves Cruz's literature combats the forgetting and silencing of these subjects, whose bodies are racialized and socio-historical, are presented as symbols of resistance, undertaking a true historical approach, of memory and our ancestry, sewing together characters, stories and open wounds since the period of slavery: one of the greatest crimes of all times.

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